

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 The PCA map among the samples of transcriptome sequencing

Figure S2 The two-dimensional map of PCA among the transcriptome sequencing samples

Figure S3 PCC analysis of the transcriptome sequencing samples

Figure S4 Distribution map of the identified miRNAs with different lengths

Figure S5 The PCA map among the samples of miRNA sequencing

Figure S6 The two-dimensional map of PCA among the miRNA sequencing samples

Figure S7 PCC analysis of the small RNA sequencing samples

Figure S8 A part of the 372 negative miRNA-mRNA interaction pairs (regulation network) in TPs. Red hexagons represented the highly expressed miRNAs in TPs. Ovals represented the target genes of miRNAs. Yellow ovals represented TFs.

